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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 28

Issue 7

Pages: 755-769

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2702

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14376203

Manuscript Accepted: 10-22-2024

A Case Study on the Parenting Stress of a Mother with Many Children

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Abstract

Motherhood is a complex process filled with boundless love, responsibility, and countless joys that can bring significant challenges, particularly when the number of children in a family increase. In the ever-evolving landscape of motherhood, it is crucial to recognize the various external factors contributing to parenting stress. Modern mothers not only struggle with the complexities of parenting but also face external pressures, such as societal expectations and the relentless pursuit of work-life balance. This research study aims to explore and observe the specific situations and problems that encountered of the Mother with Many Children including the lived experiences particularly; (1) to discuss the lived experiences of Mother with Many Children (2) to discover the challenges faced by Mother with Many Children (3) to identify the coping mechanisms of Mother with Many Children. With the use of Thematic Analysis (TA), the study findings are the following; (1) Mother with many children despite the hardship and fatigue they are facing still loves the responsibility of being a Mother with Many Children (2) Mother with Many Children are facing and experiencing parental stress wherein these individuals tend to question themselves “*anong kulang, ginawa ko naman na ang lahat.*” Other than that they also struggle when it comes to finances including; bills, school and their everyday expenses. (3) Lastly, despite the situation and experiences that they had, Mother with many children had coping strategies despite all the sacrifices, burnouts and stress they are facing whenever they see their children all together, their stress, fatigue and restlessness nights are already paid off.

Keywords: *mother, mother with many children, parental stress*

Introduction

Motherhood is a complex process filled with boundless love, responsibility, and countless joys that can bring significant challenges, particularly when the number of children in a family increase (Hoffman, 2018). Raising two or more children frequently intensifies the pressure on mothers, resulting in heightened stress levels. This stress is primarily rooted in the challenges, worries, and anxieties associated with parental responsibilities, stemming from feelings of inadequacy in meeting the demands of parenting (Qian et al., 2020). According to Azhari et al. (2019) parenting stress can hinder achieving behavioral harmony between mothers and their children. However, there remains a need to investigate whether parenting stress also influences the synchronization of brain activity during every day joint activities. Additionally, the journey of motherhood commences during pregnancy and brings about fundamental changes in a woman's physiology, endocrinology, immunological function, and behavior within the household (Guterman et al., 2019).

Thus, in the ever-evolving landscape of motherhood, it is crucial to recognize the various external factors contributing to parenting stress. Modern mothers not only struggle with the complexities of parenting but also face external pressures, such as societal expectations and the relentless pursuit of work-life balance (Copeland & Harbaugh, 2018). The pressure to succeed in all areas can be excessive at a time when women frequently balance work and a family. The pressure to be a "supermom" who balances a great career, a spotless home, and raising her children is a significant external stressor (Premaratna et al., 2022). Further, societal standards and cultural norms regarding motherhood exert a profound influence on the experiences of mothers. These norms are shaped by factors such as geographical location, ethnicity, and social class, which give rise to a broad spectrum of expectations and pressures imposed on mothers (Forbes et al. 2019). The dynamic nature of these external pressures highlights the need for comprehensive research and support systems to address the multifaceted nature of parenting stress.

Therefore, it is essential to recognize that parents face stress from their children, the high costs of child care, and the challenges of balancing work schedules (Learning Liftoff, 2018). It highlighted the importance of a mother's ability to effectively manage stress while tending to her children and fulfilling motherhood's various roles and responsibilities. Further, Schwind et al. (2023) revealed that women found early postpartum care at home to be "relieving and strengthening" as midwives coordinated patient care and provided access to relevant community-based support services. These women have reported reduced stress levels, heightened resilience, improved maternal aptitude, and increased available parental resources (Schwind et al., 2023). In addition, strategies for stress management include well-established relaxation techniques, such as taking a soothing bath, practicing meditation, engaging in regular physical activity or yoga, or simply enjoying a moment of relaxation with a cup of tea and a good book. Experts also recommend taking breaks whenever possible to unwind (Learning Liftoff, 2018)

Moreover, this study focuses on a mother with many children, aims to provide a deeper understanding of how she navigates these external stressors and the inherent challenges of raising a large family. This explores her experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms for parental stress. As the study unfolds, it will shed light on these intricate aspects of her journey. By examining the unique experiences of a mother with many children, this study intends to contribute to the existing literature by providing a comprehensive insight into the challenges and coping mechanisms such mothers employ in managing their extensive households. Furthermore, the study's potential value includes increasing awareness about the reality and challenges of having many children and

providing a forum for sharing the often-unheard experiences of families and moms confronting unusual family planning conditions. The data gathered, findings, and conclusions generated from this study will not only improve knowledge of the life of a mother with many children but will also be an excellent resource for future academics interested in diving deeper into this understudied subject area. It will provide the groundwork for subsequent studies and give insights to guide future research into understanding and assisting families with massive households.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of this research is to explore the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of a mother with many children on parenting stress. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of a mother with many children?
2. What are the challenges of a mother with many children?
3. What are the coping mechanisms for a mother with many children?

Literature Review

Experiences of a Mother with Many Children

Motherhood experiences at a young age

Being a mother to many children is a distinctive as well as challenging experience. It takes an enormous amount of love, patience, and strength. Mothers with big families frequently encounter several problems. Motherhood is crucial for women worldwide, and early-age mothers' birth narratives help them form identities within complex social, cultural, and medical worlds. Documenting these stories can break down negative stereotypes and stigmatize early-age mothers, allowing us to appreciate their strength and vulnerability despite societal broader narrative representations (Carson et al., 2016). Moreover, Childbearing women need time immediately after birth to process their experiences. Our findings highlight avenues for changes in clinical care to optimize women's experiences of unplanned cesarean births. Participants wanted clearer communication with the maternity care team, voices in the decision-making process, and inclusion of support persons to optimize their birth experiences. Because negative birth experiences affect maternal and child well-being, it is important to understand women's perceptions and develop strategies to assist them in the construction of their birth narratives (Simonelli et al., 2021). Thus, the study suggests that households with regular savings and stable income sources are more likely to achieve economic self-sufficiency. It recommends reducing regular expenses, cultivating a savings culture, and seeking opportunities to increase and maintain income (Nwoye et al., 2023). The study reveals that socioeconomic status impacts financial literacy and lifestyle, while financial literacy doesn't. To improve financial literacy, housewives should enhance education, motivate the community, and implement empowering programs for wider welfare (Sekararum et al., 2018).

Unmet need for family planning was higher in the study area when compared to the United Nations global standard and the national average, but slightly lower than the regional average. The unmet need for family planning in the research area was determined by socio-demographic, economic, and health institution characteristics. As a result, health education and behavior change communication connected to family planning services should be reinforced, as should access to family planning services (Garo et al., 2021).

Nudging to Work Overseas for a Good and Quality Life

This study explores the gender and cultural identity work women face in balancing cultural expectations and family roles as breadwinners. It reveals that financial control doesn't necessarily lead to traditional power (Carrim, 2016). Women resist family constraints despite being breadwinners.

Women's decisions to postpone having children have resulted in the development of a distinct group of women who are planning and experiencing pregnancy, childbirth, and parenthood. Previous research has shown that women in their advanced maternal age are aware of the risks associated with childbirth, with a comparative Canadian study finding that older women perceive higher risks to themselves and their baby, such as caesarean birth, dying during pregnancy, preterm birth, and having a baby born with a defect or requiring intensive care. Although some of the preparatory activities and support systems addressed in this study are not part of the healthcare system, they do have implications for practitioners seeking to improve assistance for mature-age women during their first pregnancy (Snell et al., 2020).

An uncommon occurrence or scenario can have an impact on a person's, families, or group's bio-psychosocial functioning and well-being. Families are stressed, and parents may feel increased psychological discomfort and interruptions in the parent-child interaction. Mothers' life experiences and the amount of maturity provided by age contribute to their abilities to govern their relationships in normal and challenging living situations. Moreover, studies on educational status and mother-father-child relationships have found that mothers with oppressive or conflicting mother-child relationships have lower socioeconomic conditions, and the higher the mothers' education level, the more positive their relationships with their children (Uzun et al., 2021).

In the modern world of the twenty-first century, working women have tremendous difficulty in finding enough time to balance their obligations to their families and careers. It is necessary to look more closely at how time constraints build up in both the home and

work environments in order to comprehend how working women with kids handle their limited time resources. The results of this study demonstrate that working mothers experience high levels of time pressure associated with time intensity (juggling multiple tasks and combining work and home responsibilities), time density (organizing tasks and family emotions), and time poverty (not having enough time for optional or necessary activities). When females employ techniques to boost time efficiency, it doesn't always mean that they feel less pressed for time. Women's temporal experiences are distorted and time becomes less valuable when they multitask. Employers and legislators must devise more effective strategies to motivate working men to split household and caregiver responsibilities as well as organizational tasks. These actions could lessen the time inequality and stress that women experience, especially in the home's time management control center. (Rose, 2017)

According to Craig (2016) being a parent is not only one of the most crucial rites of passage in a person's life, but it also contributes to the survival of the human species. However, for such a basic event, motherhood has become astonishingly complicated. On a social level, this is visible in delayed childbearing and falling fertility rates. Becoming a parent poses a significant dilemma, at least for women. One of the most perplexing contemporary challenges for young women is whether to become a mother, when to become a mother, and how to manage being a mother to children once born. The issue is exacerbated by the fact that child care is generally invisible, and there is no framework for social and economic accounting for it.

Profound Comprehend of Your Children Behavior and Personality

Parents provide external motivation to their children, such as encouragement, reprimanding, and understanding their talents and interests. However, internal motivation is crucial as it can be built from childhood. Parents should be role models and educate themselves on motivating children, such as attending Sunday school and acclimating them to time discipline (Purniasih et al., 2022). The study found that younger parents reported higher parental accomplishment but felt more exhausted. The number of children at home slightly increased emotional distance between parent and child. Parental traits, including neuroticism, conscientiousness, and agreeableness, were related to parental burnout, with meticulousness and lack of emotional control being risk factors and agreeableness and perseverance protective factors (Vigouroux et al., 2018).

The relationship between parents and their children is the most essential relationship that an individual may have. It is true that parents often spend the most time with their young children over lengthy periods of time. However, in the family setting, perspectives of parenting and the parent-child connection have lately broadened to include parents as active administrators of the child's social milieu. A healthy contact between parents and their children indicates a good family environment, a positive emotional component, and the existence of affective support. This relationship has a favorable impact on the child's state and behavior, and it is critical to the child's natural, physical, and mental development. This type of relationship will be hampered by family conflict (Popov et al., 2015)

Method of Disciplining Children

Pediatric providers provide guidance on parenting issues, including discipline, focusing on long-term effectiveness and mental health issues. They can explore parental feelings, define discipline goals, and offer behavior management strategies. They can also refer families to community resources. The American Academy of Pediatrics recommends healthy discipline, including positive reinforcement, limits, redirecting, and avoiding spanking, hitting, slapping, and threatening behavior (Sege et al., 2018).

Parenting is a wide concept that encompasses steady and long-lasting attitudes and practices toward child-rearing. Because mothers and fathers have various responsibilities in the family, parenting methods and practices throughout childhood and adolescence may vary based on the gender of the parents and teenagers. While gender variations in parenting are theoretically justified, the study literature in this sector is very sparse and devoid of definitive evidence on the subject. The results of this study show that women are viewed as more welcoming, responsive, and supporting than dads, as well as more behaviorally controlling, demanding, and autonomy granting. As a result, in research comparing parents on the dimensions of overall parenting styles, moms were found to be more authoritative than fathers, while fathers were seen to be more authoritarian than mothers (Yaffe, 2020)

Parental disciplinary tactics are an essential component of optimal child development. Their characteristics give danger rather than protection against the development of mental health disorders. Time-out from positive reinforcement is today one of the most widely used and well-studied disciplinary processes in the world, with overwhelming evidence supporting its usefulness and acceptability. It has also lately received significant criticism from writers that invoke attachment theory-based child well-being issues. Also evaluate what a discipline strategy should be from a mental health standpoint and generate five axioms for assessing and directing the merit and acceptability of any given discipline strategy using the best available models of developmental mental health and psychopathology (Tully et al., 2019)

Sibling Relationship

This article explores the role of sibling relationships in young children's emotional understanding and regulation. It examines conflict management, play, and sibling-parent interactions in three normative contexts. The analysis highlights the importance of identifying emotions, decoding others' emotions, anticipating responses, and using emotional understanding to influence relationships and behaviors (Kramer, 2014). Moreover, in this study discusses the importance of sibling relations in early and middle childhood,

highlighting how children's development occurs in intimate, close relationships with parents and siblings. It discusses features of different sibling interactions, such as teaching, play, prosocial behavior, and conflict, and how these interactions influence children's social skills and understanding of the social world (Howe et al., 2022)

Work Status and Life Strategy

Sing (2017) found that children of alcoholic families have lower self-efficacy and well-being compared to non-alcoholics. However, intervention programs can enhance self-efficacy, self-esteem, and well-being, enabling better personal and academic life.

Conflicts between mother and children

Adolescents' conflicts with parents can impact their autonomy and individuation, but too many can negatively impact their psychosocial adjustment and well-being. High conflicts can lead to externalizing and internalizing problems, lower self-esteem, and substance use. Understanding the conditions under which conflicts positively or negatively affect parent-adolescent relationships is crucial for realigning parent-adolescent relationships towards more egalitarianism (Branje, 2018).

Mother's Connection with her Children

This review highlights the potential benefits of Social Security (SC) for low-income families, but lacks a clear definition and specific measures, suggesting future work should clarify its conceptual understanding and develop specific measures (Plesko et al., 2021). Therefore, this study highlights the importance of considering both past and present circumstances when studying current parenting behaviors. It suggests that parental bonding history and stress experienced during childhood play a significant role in shaping these behaviors. The emotional availability scale, which assesses these factors, suggests that these factors have long-lasting effects on parent-child interactions. The study also suggests that the parent-child relationship may influence the way parenting stress and behaviors are experienced (Azhari et al., 2020)

According to Milkie et al. (2015) the quantity of time mothers spend with their children and teenagers was linked to the behavioural, emotional, and academic outcomes of their kids as well as the risky behaviour of adolescents. Mothers' engagement and accessibility with their children were evaluated. Social status characteristics were essential during adolescence and childhood, but maternal time did not affect the behaviours, emotions, or academic performance of her offspring. Spending time with parents together was linked to better outcomes for teenagers, and more maternal time was associated with fewer offenders' behaviours. In general, mothers' time matters in subtle ways, and surprisingly, only throughout adolescence. Moreover, (Gesler et al., 2023) the findings show that quality time is important. Furthermore, teens' perceptions of focused parental time are found to be more essential in determining well-being than parents' perceptions, and these beliefs have a stronger effect on life fulfillment than enrichment activities. On the other hand, enrichment activities could make up for a lack of quality shared time. Hence, in a study of (Farahnaz et al., 2021) stated that the study's findings demonstrate how crucial it is for parents to take the time to help their kids learn in Biduk-Biduk Village. This is evident from the size of the impact that parents have on their kids' learning process, which helps to foster kids' love of learning while parents fulfil their parental responsibilities. When implemented appropriately, it improves children's drive, self-discipline, and excitement in learning.

Thus, in a study of Isser (2013) This study examined the psychometric properties of 9 quantitative items assessing time scarcity and lack of energy as barriers parents face when planning and preparing meals for their children. Based on EFA, 2 new scales were created: time and energy for meals and meal planning. Measures of convergent, discriminant, and concurrent validity, as well as internal consistency reliability, provide preliminary support for both scales. The development of quantitative scales with desirable psychometric. Parents who are busy and exhausted can rapidly complete the time and energy required for meals and meal planning scales. Since many kids don't consume a healthy diet, it's important to understand the obstacles parents' experience. This will assist design treatments that are specific to the requirements of worn-out, busy parents.

Marital Status

According to Prevoo (2014) this study examines the impact of various family disruptions, such as divorce, separation, and death, on the personality development of British children enrolled in the British Cohort Study in 1970. Family disruptions before the age of sixteen are significantly correlated with early childhood personality development. The biggest detrimental influence on a child's personality development is parental divorce. When kids are older, the impacts of family disturbances on personality development are less pronounced, and the patterns vary depending on the gender. Selection has a role in the link between personality development and family disruption. Significant associations between family disruption and personality development prior to disruption are shown by means of placebo regressions. The bias resulting from the omitted variable is lessened by looking into the factors that drive the selection process.

Challenges of a Mother with 17 children

Understanding Children's Personality

Research of Darling et al. (2017) says that authoritarian rule, a set of parental characteristics that includes emotional support, high standards, appropriate autonomy granting, and clear, bidirectional communication, has been shown to aid children and adolescents in developing instrumental competence, which is defined by the balancing of societal and individual needs and responsibilities.

Responsible independence, cooperation with adults and peers, psychological maturity, and academic achievement are all characteristics of instrumental competence.

Pediatricians provide guidance to parents and guardians on child behavior management, including punishment tactics used to teach acceptable conduct and protect their children and others from the negative impacts of difficult behavior. Aversive disciplinary tactics, such as physical punishment and screaming at or humiliating children, are ineffective in the near term and ineffective in the long run. According to new research, physical punishment is associated with an increased risk of unfavorable behavioral, cognitive, psychosocial, and emotional consequences in children. (Sege et al., 2018)

Healthy communication when it comes to siblings misunderstandings

The findings suggest that both mothers and dads contribute to their children's executive functioning through their child-rearing behavior, even after adjusting for age-related improvement (maturation) and crucial factors such as gender, verbal IQ, and enrollment location. Mothers had more substantial relationships between their children's inhibition development and parenting than males. Parenting practices that entail more monitoring, less discipline, inconsistency and negative controlling, and a positive parenting style are connected with excellent inhibitory capacity development in children (Roskam et al., 2014). The way that youngsters build their connections with their siblings is greatly influenced by their parents. That being said, there aren't many evidence-based parenting programs that provide parents with the particular tools and methods they need and want to manage their kids' sibling relationships. Parents who used positive parenting techniques as opposed to punitive ones expressed high levels of acceptability, and they made it apparent that they preferred parenting treatments that were presented in formats that were simple to use. The results are explained in terms of helping to direct the creation of a customized parenting intervention aimed at improving sibling relationships and lowering conflict. (Pickering et al., 2015)

According to Sege et al. (2018) adults who, among other things, teach youngsters about acceptable behavior are needed for optimal child development. The term "discipline" comes from the Latin word "*disciplinare*," which means "to teach or train," as in disciple (a student or follower of a teacher, leader, or philosopher). Effective disciplinary strategies that are age and developmentally appropriate teach the child to regulate his or her own behavior, keep him or her safe, improve cognitive, socioemotional, and executive functioning skills, and reinforce the behavioral patterns taught by the child's parents and caregivers.

Financial crisis to Resiliency

In the study of Brastmaningtwas et al. (2022) stated that most women or housewives are in debt and they do not use their money productivity, as an outcome they will find and take new debts to pay off all the debts they have. However, in a study stated that mothers with low income are resourceful and innovative when it comes to meeting their own needs as well in their children but they face numerous challenges that are hard to manage primarily through informal support (Anderson et al., 2022)

Mothers trying to be a perfect mother

Having a lot of children is not easy to handle them all and to look after them. According to study, the norms of mothering describe women to be perfect mother, in this study stated the feeling of pressure of a mother to be perfect that will related to parental burnout, and parental stress due to avoiding mistakes as a mother (Loeg et al., 2018). Furthermore, those housewives who have a lot of tasks at home with repetitive pattern of exercise can cause fatigue and burnout in childcare, this study stated that increasing housewife self-regulation have possible effect for reduction of burnout in childcare (Haning et al., 2021)

Parental burnout is distinguished by three characteristics that resemble professional burnout while differing in that it is related to parenting: physical and emotional exhaustion; emotional distancing from one's children; and a sense of incompetence in one's parenting role (Mikolajczak, 2018). Furthermore, based on the discovery of specific risk factors for parental burnout (Le Vigouroux et al., 2017), the Parental Burnout Inventory scale was recently developed and validated (Roskam et al., 2017). Although mothers with parental burnout syndrome appear to share some of the characteristics of postpartum depression (e.g., fatigue, lack of energy), maternal burnout differs in that it occurs in mothers with children over the age of 18 months; it is predominantly linked to parental traits and, to a lesser extent, social and marital factors; and the depressive mood is not generalized but experienced in relation to one's parenting role and tasks (Tuna, 2018).

Children making their own way for paying their bills

In affluent countries, the employment engagement of women with small children has gradually grown. Combining job and family duties can cause tensions in family life, but it can also be beneficial. Work-family conflict and enrichment experienced by moms may also have an influence on children's home surroundings through parenting behavior and the marriage relationship, especially in the early years of parenting when care needs for young children are considerable. (Cooklin et al., 2015)

Sleep quality

Poor quality sleep also tended to engage in weight-related parenting behaviors that go against advice, like fewer family meals overall,

fewer meals eaten at a table, more control over kid feeding, and less frequent modelling of healthy eating and physical exercise. However, mothers who slept well admitted to engaging in unethical behaviors including rewarding kids with food and eating family dinners at fast food establishments. In addition to worse parental self-efficacy, worse general health status, more days of poor mental and physical health, more stress, and higher BMIs than comparators, mothers who reported inadequate sleep also tended to have more days of poor mental and physical health. (Eck et al., 2020). In addition, despite the fact that the total amount of sleep did not vary based on the number of children, mothers of one infant reported having less disrupted and better-quality sleep than mothers of several children. The fathers showed no variation. Thus, researchers stated that may be beneficial for healthcare professionals to create interventions that aim to distribute childcare responsibilities equally throughout the day and the night depending on the circumstances, these interventions should be customized for each family member. (Rakotomanana et al., 2021)

Multitasking

Time is a limited resource that is required for happiness (Williams et al., 2016). According to existing studies, women spend a disproportionate amount of time on unpaid housework and childcare when compared to males. However, empirical information on disproportionate time costs owing to childcare among women is lacking. (Irani et al. 2021) Mothers balance leisure and child care to a larger extent than dads across diverse national settings and policy frameworks, suggesting that the gender gap is resistant to outside institutional effects (Craig & Mullan, 2013).

Coping Mechanisms of a Mother with 17 children

In terms of spending time on household management, women play an important role because they spend more than 15 hours a day on child care and household duties. Women are moving away from their traditional role as homemakers and housewives who perform all of the household tasks; instead, women are engaging in career growth and willingly contributing to family management in the same areas as men in society. They discovered that self-esteem motivates women to participate in social welfare and decision-making (Barman et al. 2022).

According to Pareek et al. (2013) housewives must manage household obligations as well as family interactions. Furthermore, dealing with uncertainty, a lack of personal space, increased presence and interaction with people in the household, economic disruptions, a lack of domestic help, managing parental responsibility, increased stress about one's own and family members' health, and a lack of social interaction have all contributed to their discomfort. Existing data indicates that housewives are experiencing burnout in their homes. Moreover, when wealth and a set of standard characteristics are controlled for, financial concerns are related to poorer teenage cognitive and noncognitive outcomes. However, the influence of financial concerns on noncognitive results appears to be mediated by the mother's mental health (Clark et al., 2021)

Synthesis of the Review of Literature

This study, which was presented alongside a literature review, explored into themes pertinent to a case study of a mother with several children. Parenting stress can impede achieving behavioral harmony between mothers and their children, and the journey of motherhood begins during pregnancy, bringing about fundamental changes in a woman's physiology, endocrinology, immunological function, and behavior within the household. These studies provide important contributions to the study of psychology by raising awareness about the realities and challenges of having a large family and offering a venue for expressing the often-unheard experiences of families and mothers dealing with unique family planning situations (Azhari et al., 2019; Guterman et al., 2019).

However, the contrasts in other literature on this research attempted to assess how a mother/parent copes with having many children compared to only a handful. It also considers the influence on mental health or psychological elements, as well as how people manage or handle the circumstance. Emphasizing disparities in managing events, coping mechanisms, and parental responsibilities to improve knowledge of their psychological experiences. Furthermore, the stated literature provides significance to our research, giving vital linkages to improve our knowledge of having an abundance of children and the psychological issues that a mother experiences.

According to the stated above literature review, parenting is a broad concept that encompasses consistent and long-lasting attitudes and practices toward child-rearing. Because mothers and fathers have different roles in the family, parenting methods and practices throughout childhood and adolescence. Discipline from parents is an important part of a child's growth. When parents treat their children differently, it can have an impact on how siblings interact with one another. By knowing what it is, why it occurs, and how to prevent it, parents may ensure that parental uneven treatment does not become a factor that comes between siblings and degrades their relationships. The quantity of time mothers spend with their children and teens was connected to their children's behavioral, emotional, and academic results, as well as adolescent hazardous behavior. (Yaffe, 2020; Tullet et al., 2019; Milkie et al., 2015) Despite the fact that the study's specific differences and seeks aim to examine variations in Higher degrees of psychological discomfort and anxiety were connected to higher levels of perceived distress, loneliness, and housewife burnout. Despite their high anxiety and burnout rates, few studies have been conducted among housewives. Positive reinterpretation and growth, use of instrumental social support, active coping, religious coping, use of emotional and social support, suppression of competitive behaviors, and planning were the key strategies for coping. (Ridhi et al., 2021; Durak et al., 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed case study design to analyze the stress experiences of mothers who have many children. This research is challenging and hasn't gotten much attention in the past. A case study design allows the researcher to fully appreciate the participant's experiences, particularly those mothers who have so many children, and to spot trends and common threads in the instances.

The research design, which takes a qualitative case study approach, emphasizes in-depth exploration within the participants' natural context, allowing for a holistic understanding of these women's experiences, including relationships, parenting challenges, societal perceptions, and coping mechanisms. The framework for a thorough investigation of the lives, challenges, and coping methods of Mother's with many children is laid out by this all-encompassing and scientific approach to the topic, providing illuminating details on this complex social phenomenon.

Participants

The participant of this study is composed of one (1) Mother with Many Children. The participant age is fifty-nine (59) years old. Eleanor is a 59 year old mother with seventeen (17) children. She is married to her husband. She is also a housewife. All of her children are living under the same roof under the guidance of her and her husband. She did not finish her studies. She bear her child at a young age. She grew up in a complete family. She only had 1 boyfriend before her first child was born.

The participants were interviewed face to face settings by the researchers, who also recorded their responses on smartphones. The interview was conducted with the participant's consent, and the researchers further discussed the interview's purpose and process.

Instruments

This study used a semi-structured interview guide which has undergone extensive expert evaluation to ensure its dependability. To focus on the three primary themes of the study—experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of housewife's mother with multiple children—the researchers will create an interview guide with particular questions. Additionally, the participants will have the chance to explain any concepts they are unclear about or ask questions.

Procedure

The researchers interviewed the Mother with many children in semi-structured interviews to gather the data. The interviews were conducted in- person. Before the interview, participants signed a consent form to protect their confidentiality. Every participant were given a copy of the interview guide, which includes an authorization form that gives the researchers consent to record the interview for transcription purposes. The participants were assured by the researchers that all information and data is be kept private after the interview.

Data Analysis Procedure

This study employed a qualitative methodology, specifically thematic analysis (TA). TA calls for thematizing, coding, and even assessing the themes' underlying structures. Investigating the participant experiences is an adequate match for this analysis. It is a technique that can be used to explain a variety of qualitative data throughout theories.

The six stages of thematic data analysis, according to Braun and Clarke (2006; Herzog, Handke, and Hitters 2019), include data familiarization, which comprises data reading and execution, interview transcript reproduction, and seeking for patterns of relevance. Finding themes that are important or interesting patterns in the data is the goal of a thematic analysis, which may subsequently be used to discuss the research or make a point. Strong thematic analysis does more than just summarize the data; it also clarifies and makes sense of it (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017).

Additionally, there are numerous approaches to analyze qualitative data using thematic analysis. Therefore, the first outline outlines the key elements that must be taken consideration while conducting a thematic analysis (TA).

This study found that TA's adaptability may both underline and emphasize the value of serious, thorough inquiry or research. Theoretical ideas, research questions, data collecting, and data analysis can all benefit from this versatility. This study provides a thorough explanation of the steps and techniques required to carry out a TA. (Carla & Wendy, 2017)

Ethical Consideration

The data collection procedure and equipment have the study professor's approval, confirming that consent has been obtained and the principles of ethics have been properly adhered to. Participants who satisfied the defined criteria were invited to participate and gave express assent using an informed consent form with the professor's supervision.

The procedure standard for data collection was discussed, along with the informed consent form. The study's objectives and purpose were described, and the rights of the participants with regard to their voluntarily participating were made clear. They were informed that they might stop participating in the study at any moment.

Participants were promised that all information gathered during the study would be utilized only for academic and research purposes,

and confidentiality was also covered. Code names would be used to conceal their identities, and no one else would be given access to their personal data. The Data Privacy Act and Republic Act 10173 both demand this.

Results and Discussion

Case Study: Eleanor

At San Jose del Monte, Eleanor is a Mother with many children. Eleanor has been a dedicated mother to her Seventeen Children since she was 16 years old. Sessions were held on November 4th until 10th of November. She is eager to share her important experiences as a Mother with Many Children and does so with great enthusiasm. Eleanor clearly described the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms she faced. The tables show the themes emerged from the significant statements of Eleanor about her experiences as a Mother of many children.

Table 1. *Thematic analysis of Eleanor's Lived Experiences*

Themes	Subthemes
The Unstoppable Heart (Resiliency)	Raising children with good manners, with degree or not (Pleasant Personality)
	Motherhood experiences at a young age (Early Parenting)
	Nudging to Work Overseas for a Good and Quality Life (Psychological Influence)
	Disciplining Children's Behavior (Aggression)

Eleanor talked about how the experiences manifested towards her psychological well-being and the themes that emerged in the lived experiences is "*The Unstoppable Heart*" Eleanor stated that "*Ang sinasabi lang namin sa kanila lalo na nung dumami na sila hindi naming kayo kayang pag-aralin ng sabay-sabay, oo, kaya may mag tapos man sa inyo sabi ko pero ang importante maging mabuting tao kayo diba?*" (What I always tell them especially when our family is getting bigger is that we cannot afford to make them go to school all together at once, *there might some, there might not but most important is, they are a good person.*)

According to Milkie et al. (2015) the quantity of time mothers spend with their children and teenagers was linked to the behavioural, emotional, and academic outcomes of their kids as well as the risky behaviour of adolescents. Mothers' engagement and accessibility with their children were evaluated. Social status characteristics were essential during adolescence and childhood, but maternal time did not affect the behaviours, emotions, or academic performance of her offspring. Hence, in a study of (Farahnaz et al., 2021) stated that the study's findings demonstrate how crucial it is for parents to take the time to help their kids learn in Biduk-Biduk Village. This is evident from the size of the impact that parents have on their kids' learning process, which helps to foster kids' love of learning while parents fulfil their parental responsibilities. When implemented appropriately, it improves children's drive, self-discipline, and excitement in learning.

"16, 16 ako nagpakasal, oo kasi halos nagpakasal kami January, nabuntis agad ako eh kaya November ko sya pinanganak.... ang basta ang gusto ko lang apat lang talaga kaya nung nagka babae ako, kaya lang di rin na ligate pa bata pa ko non eh kaya hindi rin siguro natuloy yun ganap ako'y umabot na riyon, siguro." (I was sixteen when I got married, it was January and I got pregnant quickly so I gave birth to my first child on November. At first, I want four children only but then, things escalated quickly and we came to this point).

Motherhood is crucial for women worldwide, and early-age mothers' birth narratives help them form identities within complex social, cultural, and medical worlds. Documenting these stories can break down negative stereotypes and stigmatize early-age mothers, allowing us to appreciate their strength and vulnerability despite societal broader narrative representations (Carson et al., 2016). Teenage pregnancy is defined by the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) as conception between the ages of 13 and 19. However, the phrase "teenage pregnancy" is frequently used in daily parlance to characterize young women who fall pregnant before reaching legal maturity, which varies by country. Furthermore, while having differing meanings, the phrases adolescent, young person, and youngster are sometimes used interchangeably with teenager. This article will utilize the UNICEF definition of adolescent pregnancy. Every year, around 16 million young women give birth worldwide, accounting for approximately 11% of all births (Cook et al., 2015).

Moreover, childbearing women need time immediately after birth to process their experiences. Our findings highlight avenues for changes in clinical care to optimize women's experiences of unplanned cesarean births. Participants wanted clearer communication with the maternity care team, voices in the decision-making process, and inclusion of support persons to optimize their birth experiences. Because negative birth experiences affect maternal and child well-being, it is important to understand women's perceptions and develop strategies to assist them in the construction of their birth narratives (Simonelli et al., 2021). Thus, the study suggests that households with regular savings and stable income sources are more likely to achieve economic self-sufficiency. It recommends reducing regular expenses, cultivating a savings culture, and seeking opportunities to increase and maintain income

(Nwoye et al., 2023). The study reveals that socioeconomic status impacts financial literacy and lifestyle, while financial literacy doesn't. To improve financial literacy, housewives should enhance education, motivate the community, and implement empowering programs for wider welfare (Sekararum et al., 2018).

Due to having large family, struggling to find a decent way of money, Eleanor mentioned: “*Kaya yung time na naka graduate na yung ate nila yung nasa Japan talagang tinutukan ko sya kailangan kako, bago naman sya maka graduate ng highschool kinausap ko na yung anak ko na yun, tutal uso naman kako Japan ngayon naka graduate ka, sabi ko mag Japan ka lang muna sabi ko. Edi pumayag naman kaya nung graduate sya ng high school altimano tinutukan ko talaga yun sa pagajapan....*” (So when their older sister graduated, I talked to her and said, “Japan is trending right now, why don't you go there now that you are already finish your studies? She agreed and I helped her just for her to go there.)

Women resist family constraints despite being breadwinners. The study also explores conventional breadwinning aspects, such as career-primary, obligation, suitability, relational power, and ideal workers. Practical applications are discussed in relation to women's work-life conflict and workplace interactions (Medved, 2016). This study explores the gender and cultural identity work women face in balancing cultural expectations and family roles as breadwinners. It reveals that financial control doesn't necessarily lead to traditional power (Carrim, 2016)

“*Anak ko ayaw na mag anak edi syempre anak ko diba ang bata sa kanila mahalaga eh, eh ayaw nyan edi yan nag divorce sila ngayon dalaga naman yung anak nya ilang taon na, nasa 5 years na yata silang hiwalay...*” (My daughter doesn't want to bear a child since bearing or having a child is important to them (her Japanese boyfriend), they are divorced now.)

Women's decisions to postpone having children have resulted in the development of a distinct group of women who are planning and experiencing pregnancy, childbirth, and parenthood. Previous research has shown that women in their advanced maternal age are aware of the risks associated with childbirth, with a comparative Canadian study finding that older women perceive higher risks to themselves and their baby, such as caesarean birth, dying during pregnancy, preterm birth, and having a baby born with a defect or requiring intensive care. Although some of the preparatory activities and support systems addressed in this study are not part of the healthcare system, they do have implications for practitioners seeking to improve assistance for mature-age women during their first pregnancy (Snell et al., 2020).

When it comes to disciplining her children, Eleanor stated that: “*Kami noon ginagawa naming disiplina lalo na nung maliliit sila, pag nakipag away sila kahit kasalanan nung kaaway meron kaming mga pamalo, eh depende sa laki ng kasalanan mo merong gantong kalaki, meron gantong kahaba patpat yon, oo lalo na yung tatay nila napaka ano non strikto hindi ka pwede makipag away doon...*” (Back then, what we're doing to discipline them especially when they were still young is, who ever at fault, they will all be punished. Your punishment depends on how bad your mistakes are, the bigger your fault is, and the harder you will get hit.)

Pediatric providers provide guidance on parenting issues, including discipline, focusing on long-term effectiveness and mental health issues. They can explore parental feelings, define discipline goals, and offer behavior management strategies. They can also refer families to community resources. The American Academy of Pediatrics recommends healthy discipline, including positive reinforcement, limits, redirecting, and avoiding spanking, hitting, slapping, and threatening behavior (Sege et al., 2018).

Table 2. Thematic analysis of Eleanor's Challenges

Themes	Subthemes
Challenging the Expectation	Fostering. Understanding and Connection (Perceptive/Insightful)
	Disrespectful Behavior (Unruled Anger)
	Crisis to Resilience (Perseverance)
	Weight to Motherhood (Accountable/Obligated)

Eleanor talked about how the challenges manifested towards her psychological well-being and the theme that emerged in the challenges is "Challenging the Expectation", Eleanor stated that: “*Kapag may pagkakamali, alam mo namang mali. Syempre 'pag magulang di naman pumapayag na may mali diba? Sasabihin mo sa kanila na hindi tama 'yon. Nasa kanila naman 'yon kung makikinig sila o hindi 'di ba? Awa naman ng Diyos, nakikita ko naman na gano 'n mga anak ko...*” (If there's something wrong, and you know it. As a parent, you wouldn't tolerate that kind of actions, right? You'll tell them that it is not right. It's on their end if they will listen or not, right? Thank God, I could see my children listening.)

Research of Darling et al. (2017) says that authoritarian rule, a set of parental characteristics that includes emotional support, high standards, appropriate autonomy granting, and clear, bidirectional communication, has been shown to aid children and adolescents in developing instrumental competence, which is defined by the balancing of societal and individual needs and responsibilities.

Responsible independence, cooperation with adults and peers, psychological maturity, and academic achievement are all characteristics of instrumental competence.

Also, Eleanor encountered and challenged by disrespectful behavior of her children, she stated that: *“Sinagot ako, “Ah, ah tarantado ka kako talaga,” sabi ko, “lahat nga ginawa ko na sa ‘yo tapos sinabihan mo pa ‘kong parang wala akong-parang wala akong kwentang ina.”* (They talked backed at me. You asshole, I said. I did everything for you just for you to tell me that I am a worthless mother?)

According to Sege et al. (2018), adults who, among other things, teach youngsters about acceptable behavior are needed for optimal child development. The term "discipline" comes from the Latin word "disciplinare," which means "to teach or train," as in disciple (a student or follower of a teacher, leader, or philosopher). Effective disciplinary strategies that are age and developmentally appropriate teach the child to regulate his or her own behavior, keep him or her safe, improve cognitive, socioemotional, and executive functioning skills, and reinforce the behavioral patterns taught by the child's parents and caregivers.

Financial instability also became one of their challenges as Eleanor mentioned: *“Mahirap, mahirap talaga kung sa kailangan mo talagang magpakahirap, s’yempre nagpapalaki ka tapos dumami pa sila, oh, talagang lahat lang gagawin mo para hindi sila magutom, makapag aral kahit papano.”* (It’s hard, it is really hard, you need to work hard because they are growing older and also a growing family. You need to do everything so you can provide for their needs and finish their studies.)

In the study of Brastmaningtwas et al. (2022) stated that most women or housewives are in debt and they do not use their money productivity, as an outcome they will find and take new debts to pay off all the debts they have. However, in a study stated that mothers with low income are resourceful and innovative when it comes to meeting their own needs as well in their children but they face numerous challenges that are hard to manage primarily through informal support (Theresa et al. 2022)

“Wala nga eh, Hahaha! Ang pinaka-pahinga ko gabi, hanggang ngayon tulog lang. Sa gabi lang talaga dahil matutulog ka na, pero kung matulog pa ako minsan alas dyis. Habang hindi ako tulog, wala nag iintindi ako ng mga gagawin, liligpitin. Kaya nga sabi ko nga eh, “itong bahay namin jusko po. Kukuha ka nang makakasama mo hindi ka rin magtatagal dito kasi walang kapahi-pahinga yung gawain” hehe.” (I don’t have rest, Hahaha! My only rest is at night until now that I am older, sleep is the only rest I consider. As I’ve said, night is my only time to rest but sometimes, I sleep late, 10 pm, to be exact. I am still minding household chores whenever I can’t sleep at night. That’s why I said, this house? You’ll get someone to be with, you won’t be able to stay here longer because of the unlimited and restless chores.)

Having a lot of children is not easy to handle them all and to look after them. According to study, the norms of mothering describe women to be perfect mother, in this study stated the feeling of pressure of a mother to be perfect that will related to parental burnout, and parental stress due to avoiding mistakes as a mother (Loeg et al., 2018). Furthermore, those housewives who have a lot of tasks at home with repetitive pattern of exercise can cause fatigue and burnout in childcare, this study stated that increasing housewife self-regulation have possible effect for reduction of burnout in childcare (Haning et al., 2021)

According to the study’s findings, the Mother with Seventeen Children face both psychological, and physical difficulties brought on by the stage and difficulties relating to the demands of the family. So the responsibility of taking care of the children should not fall only on Mothers. For most mothers, a coping mechanism that should be enhanced is their social network and financial assistance.

Table 3. *Thematic analysis of Eleanor’s Coping Mechanisms*

Themes	Subthemes
Finding Love, Laughter, and Purpose (Happiness)	Dealing with Stress (Psychological Constraints)
	Children demonstrating their care for their mother (Compassionate)

Mother with Seventeen children would not be able to survive these challenges without coping strategies. In the case of Eleanor, those strategies were in the firm of dealing with stress, children caring for their mother, tactics of parenting and motherhood difficulties.

Eleanor mentioned that: *“Oo pagkaso sobra na akong stress ko na. eh pag naistress nga ako hindi lang ako nagpapakita sa mga anak ko, minsan tatago ako dyan papasok ako ng banyo dadrama na nagiiba boses ko hahahaha iiyak na ako ng iiyak oo kasi hindi ko pwedeng kimkimin eh, kapag hindi ko nilabas masakit sa mabigat dto sa dibdib parang magkakasakit ako dito sa puso. Kaya sabi ko yun nga yung pinapaiwanag ko sa kanya parang anon a rin sya parang dedma lang hindi nya na iniintindi.”* (Yes, when I cannot deal with stress anymore I would just hide in the bathroom and cry because I can’t just keep it to myself, my heart hurts.)

In terms of spending time on household management, women play an important role because they spend more than 15 hours a day on child care and household duties. Women are moving away from their traditional role as homemakers and housewives who perform all

of the household tasks; instead, women are engaging in career growth and willingly contributing to family management in the same areas as men in society. They discovered that self-esteem motivates women to participate in social welfare and decision-making (Barman et al., 2022).

Eleanor also stated that: “*Kapag alam na nilang nai stress na ko bobola bolahin na nila ko, eh natawa naman ako parang nawawala na nawawala na tapos umpisa nanaman neto “uy si nanay oo nga no, tignan mo si nanay parang ano parang ano hindi nag anak ng labing pito” hahaha ganon ganon sila. Yun nga pag alam nila naistress na ako na mag sasalita na ako ng pagalit aba’y bobola bolahin kana.*” (If they knew that I was stress, they would joke around and I will just laugh, through that, I would forget my stress. They would say “look at mom, she looks like she didn’t gave birth to a seventeen children” They would already know if I am stress if my tone of voice is changed,)

According to the book, Love and respect in the family, (2013) Parents who feel respected are more likely to respond positively to their children, and children who feel respected are more likely to respond positively to their parents. Their children. When these requirements are addressed, positive changes occur in the family. Of fact, the opposite is far too often. Unloved children behave poorly in ways that are insulting to their parents. A disrespected parent behaves harshly to the child in a way that feels unloving. Every negative action, we could say. There is an equal and opposite negative reaction in the family. Effective parenting is based on love: love that is not lenient, love that does not tolerate disrespect, but also love that is strong enough to allow children to make errors and accept the consequences of their mistakes (Parenting with Love and Logic, 2017)

Conclusion

Despite this adversity, mothers extensively demonstrate perseverance, resilience, and a tireless dedication to their family. Recognizing and valuing the difficulties of motherhood is important for creating a supportive and understanding environment that values the enormous contributions women make to the well-being of individuals and society as a whole.

A mother raising a child is already a big responsibility to do, but having a big family with many children is ten times more difficult. As the number of children grows, time management, financial responsibility, and parental burnout are some of the psychological problems that a mother may face.

In conclusion, the life of a Mother with many children demonstrates endurance, devotion, and an unending capacity for their family. As a Mother, they are responsible for providing a supportive and stable atmosphere for her huge family. The obstacles she encounters are significant, ranging from daily practical issues to emotional support, and her dedication to ensuring the well- being of each family.

The significant findings of this study’s conclusions recommend the following:

Family and Financial Planning: This study recommends comprehensive family and financial planning for Mothers who have a large family. So, individuals and couples are given the ability to make educated decisions about their reproductive life and reach their desired family size.

Time Management Seminars: Balancing the diverse needs of each child, household responsibilities, and potentially a career demands a strategic and organized approach. This study recommends all students have the information and abilities to use their time wisely and balance the needs of their children and also their own personal needs. Assisting the mother in investigating good time management and organizing techniques. Calendars, planners, and smartphone applications may help with scheduling, appointments, and domestic duties, making it simpler to manage the many obligations that come with having a big family.

Parenting Workshops and Seminars: This study recommends parenting workshops for large families that can provide unique advice and solutions. Mothers who have experience dealing with the complications of raising many children can offer practical guidance and share their own experiences related to the mother’s circumstances and can also help Mothers raising many childrens.

Support Groups: Creating organizations, support networks, family support for Mothers who has a large family like the participant to offer emotional, social, and educational help. Mothers with many children can discuss their experiences, difficulties, and coping mechanisms in these groups’ safe places.

Future Researcher: This research recommend deeper investigation into all Mothers with Seventeen Children or large families, utilizing a case study research design, it is essential for comprehensive understanding of the topic. The findings of this study encourage future researchers to take on this task. The area of Mothers with large families’ research and support systems hopes to benefit greatly from the research recommendation made in this study.

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